

 OPEN ACCESS

Manuscript ID:
IJEBAMPSR-2024-
010209

Volume: 1

Issue: 2

Month: December

Year: 2024

E-ISSN: 3065-9140

Submitted: 26-Oct-2024

Revised: 28-Nov-2024

Accepted: 06-Dec-2024

Published: 31-Dec-2024

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How to Cite this Article:

Reena Yadav¹, T. R. (2024). Social Media Marketing: The new Trends and way of Marketing for companies. International Journal of Economics, Business, Accounting, Agriculture and Management towards Paradigm Shift in Research (IJEBAMPSR), 40-47.

Social Media Marketing: The new Trends and way of Marketing for companies

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Abstract

“Social Media marketing” is one of the new and most efficient marketing and communication tools used by various organizations. “Social Media marketing” is offering and increasing unique opportunities globally. “Social Media marketing” is a trending topic, and there has not been a lot of research done yet on this. The purpose of this review paper is to let the audience know that “Social Media marketing” is beneficial for various organizations and various social institutions, through various social platforms from where the organizations can reach customers anywhere in the world, increase their brand loyalty, save costs, generate website traffic, and improve companies’ goodwill in the public eye. So, to do social media marketing, these platforms are best to do social media marketing: Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Pinterest, Twitter, Snapchat, and LinkedIn. All we must do is open an account on these platforms and try to increase the niche audience, making sure that they are loyal to your product and service. We respond to this by every day posting some good content or messages about the product on the above social media platforms. This will make the niche audience more aware of our product, that the product is still trending in the market and the product is not out of fashion, and this can increase the consumer engagement. In this review paper we have review more than 32 research paper to support our objectives. These will also help the company save money on various paid promotional tools, etc. If any customer faces any problem with a product, they can also contact the seller through these social media and can also provide some feedback to the seller. The seller will reply to the customer and try to solve the issue. This will also help the company launch the product on the market and generate sales for it.

Keywords: Social media marketing, online channels, tools technique, Marketing, Promotional Platforms

Introduction

Social media refers to a group of digital software applications and websites that allow people to create, share, and exchange various kinds of content like concepts and information via the internet. These platforms offer many features such as messaging, liking, commenting, sharing, and posting that enable the audience to connect and interact with another audience. Examples of well-known social media sites include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube. The emergence of social media has revolutionized modern communication by significantly altering how individuals link up with each other and exchange and consume content.

A marketing strategy known as "social media marketing" makes use of social media platforms to advertise goods, services, and brands. With the primary goal of boosting traffic, brand exposure, and revenue, it entails producing and disseminating blogs and material on various social media platforms to communicate and connect with a specific audience. "Social Media Marketing" has grown in importance as a component of business marketing plans. In recent years, it has come up as a powerful technique that uses social media platforms to promote the product and services. It comes after search engine optimization. After search engine optimization, organizations make various strategies and make accounts on different social platforms and websites like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, Pinterest, Snapchat, LinkedIn, Reddit, and Quora. The most important step in making a successful marketing plan is to identify the targeted market segment.

Knowing your audience is important in any marketing campaign. You need to find out who your potential customer is, where they spent their time online, and what kind of content they watch. Once you identify yourself as a potential customer, you're the best platform to reach them.

After creating accounts, these companies make content to attract their targeted audience. They provide material aligned with the organization's objectives. Social media provides a distinctive commercial communication approach (Eagleman, November 2013). They also try to tempt the audience through its message and make them buy its product. This is one of the best methods to reach a worldwide audience. These are a very cost-effective technique of marketing strategy. Social media also helps the company to provide a competitive edge over its competitors. Through social media, there will be a better understanding and relationship between the company and its customers. By using social media, customers can give their feedback and grievances in the social handles of the company in their comment sections, and the company tries to reply and solve the problems. They also try to improve the product according to the needs of the customers. "Social Media Marketing" has the power to alter the character and structure of a company in addition to generating a lot of opportunities. The social media trend offers a research opportunity as well as a means of commercial expansion.

Why have I selected this topic?

"Social Media Marketing" helps in reaching the targeted niche-oriented segments, whether by paying for ads or free promotion in social media. "Social Media Marketing" helps increase customer engagement and response by creating goodwill for the company's product in their minds. Social media also helps companies build trust in the public's eye through quality content. The better the quality of blogs, videos, and images about the product, the more people will have confidence in buying it. The production of information and collaboration among users via the online application for marketing activities (Kaplan, (2015)) attracts new customers (Michaelides, 2011). As (Michaelides, 2011) note, using social media does not require a huge investment but very little or no cost.

"Social Media marketing" is a new technique of marketing in the market, and very little research has been done till now. But it is a trending topic because the population of our earth is increasing, so there needs to be an increase so to fully fill their needs and reach their social media are playing a crucial role in promoting them online, so "Social Media Marketing" acts as a bridge

between the organization and the customers. because the SMM organization is not only able to reach customers but is also able to fully fill their needs and remove their problems regarding the product provided by that organization.

The objective of Social Media Marketing

1. To find out the importance of using "Social Media Marketing" by Companies.
2. To Find out the importance of various "Social Media Marketing" Platform companies can Use to promote their products and services

Advantages of Social Media Marketing

1) Reach:

According to (Chaubey, January 26, 2022), "there are 4.55 billion active social media users globally", but this number is more than the previous year by 9.9%. This huge population base means the business can tap into social media platforms to connect with potential customers. for that, the business must make a great business strategy, this will be done through social media marketing. Different audience uses a different type of platform according to their circle for example for the young generation Instagram and Snapchat is a better platform, while for their parent Twitter and WhatsApp is a better platform, for B-to-B LinkedIn, for B to C Facebook is a better platform as compared to others, Facebook also has the highest number of users. so, to reach more and more audience company must plan accordingly, cause the significance of "Social Media Marketing" is that it has the potential to reach customers.

2) Improved brand loyalty:

Brands that communicate and participate on social media platforms have more client loyalty, according to a Taxes Tech University survey. As to the survey, businesses must use the resources provided by social media. In terms of interacting with clients, 53% of Americans are more devoted to companies that they follow, according to another Convince and Convert survey.

3) Increase website traffics:

By sharing links to your brand's website or product on your social media handles and encouraging your followers to visit your site. You can do this by creating more tempting and catchy headlines, content, and visuals that will increase website traffic. You can also run paid ads on various social media platforms, those who click on that ad will directly reach your website. If they like your product then they will also try to buy that product.

4) Cost-effective:

According to (Weinberg, 2009), the main advantage of "Social Media Marketing" is cost

related. According to HubSpot, 84 % of the marketer found “Social Media Marketing” a more efficient form of marketing than any other form of promotion Traditional marketing like promotion via television advertisements or print advertisements can be very expensive and may not guarantee the desired result, while “Social Media Marketing” can be very cheap or little cost it is cost-effective as compared to the traditional way of marketing

5) Increase brand awareness:

Social media allows businesses to reach many customers and increase their brand awareness. According to reports by the (Beer, 2018), 54% of people use browsers to research products, and 71% of the customers who have a positive experience with that brand try to recommend it to others. By creating a strong brand presence on social media businesses can increase their reach and try to attract more new customers.

6) Improve customer insight:

Social media listening, such as keeping an eye on user comments and what people are saying about your brand, provides several opportunities to learn important information about what consumers want, are interested in, and how they act. .by responding to all queries and problems faced by the customer, rectifying and improving the product according to the customer’s will and need, will help the company in improving customer services. According to Sprout Social, report 83% of consumers says it is important that the brand they are using should respond to their queries and concern on social media

Various social media Handles through which the business promotes its business

Over the past 30 years, there have been some important changes that how a business is promoting its brand and product online and how people are reacting and supporting it. The introduction of 4G and 5G networks has a great impact on how business functions interact and promote. Every social media platform provides a chance to showcase oneself and one’s goods to a dynamic audience and potential customers. (Roberts, 2008), social media has influenced information from acquisition to after-buying behavior (Marygold and Faulds 2009) and “Pattern of internet usage” (Rose et al 2009, Larache et al 2012) has a great impact on buying behavior of customers. In the past couple of years, various companies’ marketing strategies have increased significantly using social media. some of the most trending social handles are Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Pinterest, Snapchat, LinkedIn, Quora, Instagram, etc.

Facebook

Facebook was launched in 2004. Facebook is the seventh most valuable corporation in the world, with 2.93 billion monthly users, or 36.7% of the global population, according to Hootsuite. Additionally, it ranks third globally in terms of website traffic. Facebook posts more than one billion stories per day. This app is popular among the aged 25-34. Facebook is used 19.7 hours a month by various users. American spend 30.1 minutes a day. It gives marketers the most data and targeted ads Facebook has all your data.

Reasons why you should use Facebook

- It has many users
- It helps in building your brand loyalty
- It is easy to reach your targeted customers by using Facebook
- Facebook dominates social sakes in the market
- It also helps you in increasing your web traffic

Pinterest

Pinterest is one of the platforms for businesses to connect with the audience, whether it is B2B marketing or B2C marketing .it helps businesses in raising brand awareness, and community building, increase website traffic, and improve customer relationships. In Pinterest, we pin photos or videos to a board and add links to your website. this not only promotes your website but also increases traffic to your website. Pinterest is the 3rd most popular social media in the USA. it is mainly used by women its users are highly engaging at 14.2 minutes per visit.

Reasons why you should use Pinterest.

It helps the business in driving traffic to their websites

It gives the business some analytical tools to track business performance

It is a great platform for travel fashion beauty and food products

It also business to demonstrate its product and services

It helps businesses in increasing search engine ranking

Twitter

Since its founding in 2006, Twitter has amassed 450 million monthly active users, according to Demand Sage. Every day, 500 million tweets are sent, and 80% of those tweets include a brand reference. Twitter is the fourteenth most popular social media platform, according to sprout social. Tweets containing images get 18% more retweets and click-throughs. Twitter combines social networking with microblogging (Borges 2009). Users may advertise on Twitter and get brief updates from manufacturers (Hafele 2011).

Reasons why you should use Twitter

- It helps in boosting sales with special offers and discount
- It helps in connecting to customer

- It provides pieces of information to customers
- It also helps in creating brand awareness
- It also helps the business in building companies' goodwill

LinkedIn

LinkedIn was founded in 2003, According to social shepherd LinkedIn has 875 million users, and LinkedIn is one of the oldest social media platforms. About 134.5 million users daily use LinkedIn. It has over 58 million companies. It has users between the ages of 25 to 34 years old. After the USA, India has the highest number of LinkedIn users. You will find that on average users spend 17 minutes monthly on LinkedIn.

1 billion endorsements on LinkedIn. Even every minute, 8 people are hired on LinkedIn according to social shepherd.

Why should you use LinkedIn?

LinkedIn can be used to campaign to a specific group of people.

- It helps in generating traffic for your website as well as your product
- It is good for B2B businesses.
- It helps businesses in reaching more professional audiences
- It helps in increasing awareness
- It helps in building relationships with your followers through which you gather information, holds a discussion, and connect directly with your audience

• **Instagram**

Instagram was founded in 2010. According to Hootsuite is the 8 most visited website in the world. it has 2 billion active users monthly. This is the most popular app among 12 to 17-year-old people. 80 % of the accounts follow a business account on Instagram. India has the most Instagram users in the world. 300 million+ accounts use Instagram per day. About 40 billion numbers of photos have been shared to date. 4.2 billion number of likes per day. any post that has one hashtag gets more engagement. Instagram is used by 25.31 % of the world's population.

The reason why you should be on Instagram

- It has more young users than any other social platform in the world.
- Through Instagram many businesses are promoting the business and generating self-employment for various bloggers, content creators, and famous personalities.
- It promotes influence marketing
- It also sales for businesses via social influencers
- It has a lot of visual content

You tube

YouTube was founded in 2005, according to Hootsuite "YouTube has 1.7 billion monthly visitors". On YouTube, on average, 19 minutes are

spent by visitors a day, and about 99% of YouTube users have social media accounts on different platforms. "YouTube is the second most visited website in the world". Every minute, 694000 hours of video are broadcast on YouTube. 2.56 billion people might see YouTube advertisements.

The reason why you should be on YouTube

- It helps businesses to tap massive audiences.
- It also uses to re-purpose what you have already created
- It helps businesses to grow their audience internationally.
- It also helps you to increase traffic to your website
- It helps in increasing sales

• **Snapchat**

Snapchat was founded in 2011. according to HubSpot Snapchat has 186 million daily users, Snapchat users share more than 3 billion snaps per day, and users also watch 10 billion videos every day on Snapchat. on average time spent per user daily is 30 minutes. Active Snapchat users open the Snapchat app 18+ times a day .it also has a young audience. if you are selling products to young people and you are not on Snapchat then you are doing something wrong.

Reasons why you should be on Snapchat

- It will drive customers for you.
- It will also help businesses in building awareness, plenty of big brands use Snapchat to promote their business.
- It is the best platform to connect with the young segment of society and attract new followers.
- It is designed to connect brands with the "discover" icon means users can see content created by brands.
- It gives your follower a chance to reply and send you direct messages and help in building trust.

Methodology

This study is using the secondary data which has been collected from the various published research paper/studies, articles, websites. An analysis has been done in through the literature review.

To examine the wide literature Social Media Marketing: The new Trends and way of Marketing for companies, it was essential to read 32 papers connected to the issue. Regarding the selection of journals (journals search articles from and journals were examined when producing the review paper), time range (mainly current publications were picked). We analysed 32 publications published in academic journals from 2000-to 2024. After the selection of papers and reading the papers, the content was sorted according to the study subject, year of publication, methodology, aim, and purpose. After reading

different study papers connected to Social Media Marketing: The new Trends and way of Marketing for companies, articles were categorized as per themes in a table which was reflecting upon the same subject. similar, tables were developed to acquire a knowledge of the issue in detail.

We located papers that fit these criteria by doing a systematic keyword search in major databases such as Emerald, Springer, Wiley, Scopus, academia.edu, Google scholar, and the databases of major websites for literature review

Discussion

In this part, we reflect on the data obtained on Social Media Marketing: The new Trends and

way of Marketing for companies and its present status.

Citation	Topic	Objective	Methodology	Findings
(Fan, 2023)	“Social Media Marketing Strategies”	Determine “Social Media Marketing” techniques. Examine the advantages, obstacles, and evolving trends in marketing.	Strategies for “Social Media Marketing” Employment of contemporary technology in marketing	“Social Media Marketing” tactics augment brand recognition for enterprises. Organizations inadequately use creativity and inventive potential owing to a lack of information about available tools.
(K., 2023)	“Trends of digital Social Media Marketing affecting startups in Indian economy”.	Identify contemporary trends impacting Indian startups' marketing. Examine technical advancements and emerging marketing terminologies for 2023.	Structured questionnaire for primary data gathering from 100 respondents. Data analysis and hypothesis testing using chi-square test.	Identify contemporary trends impacting Indian startups' marketing. Analyse technology developments and new marketing vocabulary for 2023.
(Pintu, 2020)	“A prospective venue for Marketing is Social Media Marketing”.	Analyse “Social Media Marketing” concepts and methods. Explore social media's function and value in marketing.	“Social Media Marketing” across multiple platforms Utilizing data analytics techniques for assessing campaign efficacy	“Social Media Marketing” transforms firm communication and engagement. Companies employ analytics for effective social media strategy.
(Maryna, 2022)	“Digital marketing as a novel tool for goods and services promotion on social media: contemporary	Highlight aspects of digital marketing tool creation. Emphasize digital marketing's significance in	Highlight aspects of digital marketing tools for product promotion. Outline trends and progress of digital	Digital marketing is vital for accomplishing corporate objectives. Trends in digital marketing technologies mirror socio-economic trends.

	trends and development directions”	accomplishing corporate objectives.	marketing in marketing management.	
(Samita, (2023))	“Social Media Marketing: Strategies and Impact on Business.”	Explore “Social Media Marketing” tactics for companies Compare effect of “Social Media Marketing” with conventional techniques	Selecting suitable platform, generating interesting content, using influencer partnerships Comparing efficacy and impact of social media with conventional techniques	“Social Media Marketing” is crucial for company engagement. It assists micro and small firms tremendously.
(Nataliia, 2023)	“Social Networks as a Tool of Marketing Communications”.	Analyse social networks as commercial communication tools. Implement social networks in firms' marketing strategy.	Theoretical and methodological approaches Analysing the possibilities of leveraging social networks	Social networks are effective tools for marketing communications. Implementing marketing initiatives using social networks helps firm tactics.
(Natalya, 2021)	“Performance of Social Media Marketing Communications of Industrial Companies”.	Develop and test technique for analysing social media performance. Identify SMM tactics impacting brand awareness and search inquiries.	Correlation analysis, one-way ANOVA test, t-test Testing assumptions regarding social media activity and SEO promotion performance	The paper notes that “Social Media Marketing” (SMM) gives industrial organizations chances to boost brand recognition and sales via focused communication, content production, and interaction, underlining the necessity for a strategic strategy to properly exploit these digital marketing tools.
(Sonal, 2021)	“Social Media Marketing as New Marketing Tool”.	Discuss “Social Media Marketing” thoughts and techniques. Provide real instances of firms employing social media marketing.	Utilizing social media as a specialized apparatus Making firms visible to those interested in their goods	Social media is a crucial marketing medium. Companies utilize it to engage and target consumers.
(Yatish, 2023)	“Social media influencer marketing: foundations, trends, and ways forward”	Systematic study of social media influencer marketing literature. Identify essential topics, methodologies, and structures in study.	Multi-method systematic literature review Bibliometric-content analysis	Major themes: Parasocial interactions, sponsorship, authenticity, engagement, impact. Factors affecting customer reactions: Audience, brand, content, influencer, social, technology.

Scope for Future Studies

“Social Media Marketing” is a significant for both domestic and international companies. By studying Social Media Marketing: The new Trends and way of Marketing for companies. Companies can make policies and strategies and do marketing promotions accordingly, so after doing a literature review, writers can do primary research on the same topic “Social Media Marketing: The new Trends and way of Marketing for companies and

lasting and perishable products in the future by filling out a standardized questionnaire from respondent.

Conclusion

“Social Media Marketing” is an essential part of a company’s marketing strategy that aims to promote products, services, and brands through social media platforms. It helps businesses connect with their niche audience, increase brand

awareness, and build customer loyalty. “Social Media Marketing” provides a cost-saving method to reach worldwide customers and create a competitive edge over competitors. Identifying the targeted market segment, creating quality content, and engaging with customers through online interaction are crucial steps for a successful social media campaign. The scope of “Social Media Marketing” includes various activities such as customer support, media campaigns, content planning, and analysis of customer preference. Overall “Social Media Marketing” is a powerful tool or way for businesses aiming to expand and succeed in the current digital age.

Acknowledgments

I am Sukurulla Shaikh thankful to Ms Meenu Sharma HOD, Department of Management, DPG Degree College for granting permission to carry out the work

Financial support and sponsorship

Nil.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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